

Peter, Gabriel Simon; Dr Sunday Ibanga & Prof. Nkanikpo Ibok

ELECTRONIC ADMINISTRATION AND SERVICE DELIVERY IN AKWA IBOM STATE UNIVERSITY, NIGERIA FROM THE YEAR 2015 TO 2023

¹PETER, GABRIEL SIMON; ²DR SUNDAY IBANGA;

³PROF. NKANIKPO IBOK

^{1&2}Department of Public Administration

³Department of Marketing, Akwa Ibom State University

08057170802

mail.gabrielpeter@gmail.com

Abstract

Utilisation of computer and ICT tools has been identified as a necessity in contemporary university administration. In the 21st century, the use of computers and other ICT gadgets has become a mainstay in enhancing service delivery as it reduces stress, enhances speedy service, and reduces errors. This study, therefore, sets out to examine electronic administration and service delivery in Nigerian universities, using Akwa Ibom State University as a case study, with the aim of examining the effect of e-administration on service delivery at Akwa Ibom State University from 2015 to 2023. Adopting the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), this research seeks to ascertain whether online admission has significantly promoted service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University from 2015 to 2023; to determine the effect of utilisation of online payment methods on service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University from 2015 to 2023; and to determine whether computer-based testing has resulted in efficient service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University from 2015 to 2023. The research methodology adopted for the study was both qualitative and quantitative, while the research design was a descriptive survey. The sources of data were both primary and secondary. Questionnaires were administered to a sample size of 400 respondents drawn from Akwa Ibom State University using the Taro Yamane formula (N). Data collected were analysed using correlation and simple linear regression analysis through the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). Findings showed that online admission processing, online payment methods, computer-based testing, etc. have significantly impacted service delivery at Akwa Ibom State University within the period under review. It was recommended that e-administration be sustained to ensure the smooth running of universities in Nigeria.

1. Introduction

The 21st century has witnessed tremendous advancements in technology, and this has far-reaching implications on the administration and management of all sectors, particularly the education sector. The adoption and integration of electronic administration, that is, the application of information and communication technology (ICT) in all areas of administration for the main purpose of improving the delivery of public services, is paramount in academic institutions. It addresses the problems associated with the traditional method of carrying out administrative and ancillary functions of day-to-day activities. As an alternative management framework, e-administration can reduce the cost of administration, improve transparency and speed, optimise the institutions' objective function, and provide access to data and information needs of the community (Joshua, Joshua, & Ikiroma, 2014; Abdulkadir, 2017).

The way in which the functions of service delivery are performed at tertiary institutions has undergone changes over time. Earlier, service delivery was carried out in a traditional or old manner, characterised by a highly bureaucratic method with many paper-based and long procedures. This method gave rise to delays in services, poor quality services, a lack of transparency, and much room for corruption (Arkes, 2015; Amukugo & Peters, 2016). Massive complaints by graduated students, retired staff, and other stakeholders have been recorded on the status of service delivery in public institutions, especially in Nigeria. With the old or traditional method, administrative functions are not carried out in the most effective and efficient manner. The process of admission, for instance, requires that applicants travel from their various homes to the institutions to purchase, fill out, and submit forms along with the relevant documents. The process therefore distorts the smooth operations of the entire institution and has adversely affected efficient service delivery to the citizens (Mormah, 2014; Eneh, 2015).

It is in response to the identified deficiencies that institutions and organisations, through the use of information and communication technologies, are introducing innovations for better delivery of services, breaking bureaucratic barriers, reducing corruption, and equipping staff with the right technological tools (Dolfsma & Seo, 2013; Montargil, 2010). The e-administration trend has found its way into many sectors. In academic institutions, there has been an impressive utilisation of this to enhance effective service delivery. For example, the e-administration practices in the institution management system have given rise to memos and emails, which are now being distributed online instead of manual dispatch; transcripts, verification, and confirmation are now done electronically; payment of school fees is now done through remita or e-transact; course registration and publication of in-course examination results are available; e-documentation of students' academic records, Computer-Based Test,

electronic library services, and e-learning are among the innovations resulting from e-administration.

Service delivery is a major need for any organisation; it is the process of getting services done as effectively and quickly as possible to intended recipients. According to reference.com (2018), service delivery is a component of business that defines the interaction between providers and clients where the provider offers a service, whether it is information or a task, and the client either finds value or loses value as a result. Good service delivery provides clients with an increase in value. E-administration has been perceived to be effective in improving service delivery through the use of technology. As a matter of fact, e-administration makes for more efficiency and effective service delivery in institutions like Akwa Ibom State University, especially in the 21st century, in tandem with what is obtained in most tertiary institutions in the country, which are rapidly keying into the use of information and communications technologies (ICTs) in their management, teaching, learning, and research.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

E-administration has over the years gained its course in Nigerian higher institutions mainly because of the mandate by regulatory bodies like the National University Commission (NUC) and the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) that tertiary institutions should be assessed and ranked through the level of functionality of their websites, network structures, associated academic portals, and overall ICT compliance. Many institutions have now keyed into the global demand for information and communication technology applications, though with several challenges like inadequately proficient manpower, a low rate of acceptability, and an initial take-off cost, which consequently leave stakeholders highly dissatisfied and discouraged.

In offering efficient services to prospective students, for example, some tertiary institutions have dedicated some employees to handle admission processing and provide useful information to prospective candidates. However, most candidates stay far away from the campuses and may not be able to visit the school premises for the purpose of processing their admissions manually. To ameliorate this, most tertiary institutions in Nigeria have adopted the online admission process for enrolling prospective students to ease the stress. There are still others who have not yet been able to acquire the technological tools and workforce necessary for facilitating these services. Most of the new entrants are novices in the use of ICT and sometimes get frustrated trying to process their admission online. Furthermore, poor internet services and information infrastructure, as well as a low level of technological development in the country, have made accessibility a big challenge.

Also of note are the problems associated with payment of fees by candidates and students. In view of the outrageous crowd at banking halls, there have been incidents of unnecessary delays while queuing up to make payments for fees. In view of this, some tertiary institutions have introduced the use of online payment methods. However, there are some problems associated with this method. These problems include inadequate financial resources to enable institutions to acquire the latest versions of ICT infrastructure to enhance efficiency, a lack of staff training, the high cost of maintaining ICT infrastructure, the poor acceptability of the new processes, the absence of a policy framework, and the vandalization of ICT equipment, which further makes the adaption and integration of e-administration a herculean task.

The above challenges have far-reaching implications on almost all aspects of educational administration and, consequently, service delivery. Having noted these challenges, the work intends to examine the level of adoption and integration of electronic administration in the management of Akwa Ibom State University and the effect on service delivery. The study also intends to discover ways e-administration could be strengthened to enhance efficiency so that these institutions will remain centres of intellectual excellence in a global setting.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

While the general objective of this research is to examine the effect of e-administration on service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University, its specific objectives include:

1. To ascertain the effect of online admission processing on service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University
2. To determine the effect of utilisation of online payment methods on service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University
3. To ascertain the impact of the utilisation of computer-based testing (CBT) on service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University

1.4 Research Questions

1. To what extent has online admission processing affected service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University?
2. How has the utilisation of online payment methods impacted service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University?
3. To what extent has the utilisation of computer-based testing (CBT) impacted service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between online admission processing and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.
2. There is no significant relationship between online payment methods and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.
3. There is no significant relationship between the utilisation of computer-based testing (CBT) and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Electronic Administration

1. Hornby (2012) defined administration as the planning, organisation, and successful operation of a business or organisation. Tertiary institutions' administration involves the means of operation, organisation, and management. Bleiklie (2007) emphasised the role of administration in steering higher educational institutions and managing processes to achieve desired outcomes, goals, and stakeholder satisfaction.

E-administration is a crucial aspect of e-governance in the education sector, with scholars often using the terms interchangeably. For significant reforms in tertiary education, improvements in information and communication technology (ICT) are necessary for teaching, administration, and research technologies. The World Bank (2002) recommended electronic networking for teaching, learning, research, management, performance, and monitoring of systems. ICT refers to technologies that provide access to information through telecommunication devices like computers, wireless networks, cellular phones, and the internet. It is essential to clearly define ICT's meaning in this context.

According to Mormah (2014), e-administration is one of the knowledge explosions, and it is all about a system of administration whereby the traditional art of initiating, planning, organising, analysing, directing, budgeting, and coordinating all factors of production to achieve organisational goals is electronically processed with little or no paper and the stress of movement of files and documents from one office or table to the other. E-administration is an effective mechanism for achieving organisational objectives through the adoption of electronic devices in carrying out administrative functions of day-to-day activities.

Nigerian tertiary institutions are embracing e-administration to streamline their operations, including admissions, examinations, learning, assessment, library services, record management, and payment systems. However, there are still areas where the electronic administrative system needs improvement. For example, electronic

Peter, Gabriel Simon; Dr Sunday Ibanga & Prof. Nkanikpo Ibok

distribution of memos and emails, transcripts, verification, and confirmation, as well as electronic payment of fees, course registration, examination results, and academic records, are being implemented. Additionally, computer-based tests, electronic library services, and e-learning are being implemented. The integration of information and communication technology in administration is seen as a key to enhancing service delivery and transformational development.

2.1.2 Service Delivery

Service delivery in tertiary institutions is heavily influenced by external and internal factors such as workforce remuneration, training, promotional procedures, and system culture (Budhiraja, 2015). However, service delivery is highly dependent on information technology and the skills and knowledge of employees in those tertiary institutions. The availability of ICT and a skilled workforce are essential for e-administration, along with leadership, regulatory frameworks, financial resources, organisational conditions, and information and technology infrastructure. Skills targeted at specific categories of employees include those of deans of faculty, heads of departments, administrative officers, IT specialists, and others. Implementing e-administration solutions requires new administrative and technical skills to plan, evaluate, manage, finance, and integrate information systems as part of administrative operations (Settles, 2015).

According to Adegboyega, Tomasz, Elsa, and Irshad (2017), information technology (IT) skills are technical skills necessary to implement e-administration in order to facilitate smooth service delivery through improved information management. These may include basic IT literacy for all employees and technical skills for IT specialists to design and implement technical elements: hardware, software, and communication of e-administrative initiatives.

E-administration in Tertiary Institutions

Higher institutions worldwide play a crucial role in human capital formation, equipping students with advanced competencies to compete in the globalised world and effectively manage national affairs. They provide design, teaching, and research, enhancing scientific and technological advancements, indigenous technology, and capabilities in agriculture, health, and security. Tertiary institutions also offer lifelong learning opportunities, allowing individuals to upgrade their knowledge and skills based on societal needs (Shrivastava, Raizada, & Saxena, 2014). However, managing tertiary institutions requires an efficient method of delivering services, such as electronic administration, which ensures efficient, cost-effective, and accessible delivery. In

Nigeria, tertiary institutions have not yet integrated e-administration into their departments and units.

2.1.3 E-Examination (Computer-Based Test)

Testing in the education sector is crucial for evaluating the educational system's effectiveness. Despite educational goals and curriculum organisation, without accurate evaluation and reporting of learning progress, these efforts would be wasted (Duze, 2011).

Traditional methods, such as oral, written, practical, theoretical, and electronic assessments, have been used to evaluate an individual's abilities. In Nigeria, the traditional method of assessment is the predominant mode, using pen on paper to assess cognitive abilities. However, this method has been criticised for malpractices such as unauthorised materials, writing on currency notes and identity cards, spying on other candidates, substituting answer sheets, and changing scores or grades. Other malpractices include impersonation, body writing, and tattooing, particularly among female students. Therefore, proper evaluation and reporting of learning progress are essential for a successful educational system (Mubashrah, Tariq, & Shami, 2012).

E-examination, or computer-based assessment, is a modern method of administering examinations where responses are electronically recorded or assessed. According to Bennett (2015), computer-based test replaces traditional pen-on-paper formats and combines networks, hardware, software, communication, collaboration, and engagement. It can be understood to be a complex of artificial techniques and knowledge for solving problems associated with marking pen-on-paper examinations (Bennett, 2015). Computer-based testing (CBT) is a catalyst for change in learning, pedagogy, and curricula in educational institutions. CBTs are questions, problems, or practical tasks issued on a computer to gauge knowledge, ability, or experience. They can deliver more accurate and reliable results than traditional examinations. Traditional methods of assessment are being replaced by automated assessment, and administrators worldwide are migrating towards using CBT to test students' knowledge (Conole & Warburton, 2005).

2.1.4 Benefits of E-Examination

Specifically, the benefits of computer-based test spread across the shortcomings of paper-based test methods. Olatoye (2014) itemised the benefits of CBT, which are:

i. Improved Measurement Precision and Efficiency: The capacity of the computer to associate with and tailor itself to the understudy being tested. A CBT with these capacities is called versatile. As a versatile test continues, answers to prior

inquiries figure out which inquiries are asked later. The test, therefore, logically changes as the understudy's execution level is slowly uncovered.

ii. Increased Convenience: A major benefit of computerised testing is operational convenience for students, test administrators, and those who use test scores. These conveniences include:

- **Self-administering:** Regular paper-and-pencil tests for the most part oblige somebody to disseminate test booklets and answer sheets, monitor time points of confinement, and gather materials after the test closes. Overseeing a CBT can be as straightforward as stopping an understudy before a computer.
- **Immediate Scoring:** The estimation of any data debases after some time. A score report based on a test taken a month and a half prior is a portrayal of what that understudy was instead of what she or he at present is. CBTs can address this qualification by giving understudies score reports on an endless supply of their tests. The test can, along these lines, have a momentary effect. At the understudy level, this may include rapidly changing the instructional approach to a specific idea. At the school or local level, prompt data may permit comparative, however, more worldwide strategic movements.
- **Integrated Information Administration Frameworks:** Testing on computers can enable scores to be entered naturally into classroom, school, region, or state-level databases. Once there, different individual and total reports can without much of a stretch be created to condense and track the execution of individual understudies and characterised gatherings.
- **Diagnostic Appraisal and Combination with Instructional Programming:** Self-delegating, prompt scoring, and simple information administration make CBTs—versatile CBTs specifically—perfect for demonstrative or developmental appraisal. Consider the issue of evaluating an understudy's example of qualities and shortcomings over a genuinely wide substance space.

Furthermore, according to Abubakar and Adebayo (2014), advocates of CBT have identified many positive prospects of this approach to assessment as follows:

- i. More efficient than paper-based tests
- ii. Year-round testing
- iii. Flexible scheduling
- iv. Individualized testing environment

- v. Faster score reporting, within approximately two weeks of testing
- vi. Immediate viewing of scores on screen
- vii. Convenient to undergraduates, graduates, and the larger university community
- viii. Ability to access all tests that are demanded by students and the community at large
- ix. Worldwide testing opportunities for distance and traveling students
- x. Local and centralized registration and billing systems
- xi. Enhanced consistency and security.

2.1.5 Traditional Examination: This refers to a formal examination administered through question papers to which students respond in the form of written answers to a limited choice of previously unseen examination questions set in advance and answered in examination centres where invigilators (examination supervisors) prevent communication between students and prohibit the use of notes or other revision aids (Harris, 2005). These exams are conducted in examination centres, where invigilators prevent communication and the use of notes. However, these methods can be problematic due to issues such as venue capacity constraints, lack of comfort for candidates, delayed results, malpractices, cost implications, and human errors (Obasi, 2009; Nwaorgu, 2012). In addition, students may refuse to submit answer scripts when they are not well-prepared, especially in large-scale courses. Abubakar and Adebayo (2014) also observed that the traditional method of examination assesses students only on cognitive abilities, while e-examination can be used to assess both cognitive and practical abilities. E-examination, on the other hand, can assess both cognitive and practical abilities using e-testing software and e-portfolios or simulation software. Automated assessment, when designed carefully, can comprehensively and reliably assess students in the three domains of learning (cognitive, psychomotor, and affective) (Obioma, Junaidu, and Ajagun, 2013).

Assessments according to the NPE (2013) are designed for the following goals as provided in section 151(iv):

- i. To accurately measure the abilities of students;
- ii. Enhance the global competitiveness of the products of the Nigerian educational system;
- iii. Improve the credibility of examinations conducted in Nigeria;
- iv. Eliminate the intractable problems associated with the traditional paper pencil test (PPT); and
- v. Improve learning.

Peter, Gabriel Simon; Dr Sunday Ibanga & Prof. Nkanikpo Ibok

The foregoing enumerated goals demonstrate explicit realisation in the chapters of the sixth edition of the National Policy on Education that the PPT is fraught with challenges that have insurmountable solutions (Onu, 2017). Consequently, the NPE (2013) recognised the benefits of using ICTs in examination management as a possible sustainable solution. It thus encouraged providers of all levels of education in Nigeria to migrate to the current and more sufficient way of testing by adopting electronic testing models.

On Section 151(C), the NPE was specific when it observed that, in pursuance of the goals enumerated in Section 151(i-v), as stated above, all levels of education in Nigeria shall be encouraged to migrate to a computer-based testing mode of assessment (Baker-Eleleth, Emeleth, O'Neill, & Stone, 2006; Fagbola, Adignn, & Oke, 2013; Fluck, Pullen, & Harper, 2009). Obviously, with the above provisions, the management of tertiary institutions is speedily keying into the use of CBT in examination conduct assessment. The move is supposed to ensure academic integrity and quality assurance in the system.

2.1.6 E-Payment:

Electronic payment is a method of making and collecting payments electronically, enabling quick and efficient transfers of funds. It is also known as an online payment system or electronic payment system. The system connects bank accounts and facilitates monetary transactions through bank deposits (Summers, 2012).

It entails creating a platform for individual student fees and providing information such as name, department, registration number, level or class, date of payment, amount paid, academic session or semester, bank's name, account number, phone number, school name, and other personal records. This improves prompt payment and safe delivery, preventing financial frustration for management and students (Jelilove & Musa, 2016; Mustapha, 2018; Omotubora & Basu, 2018).

In Nigerian higher schools, students' payment systems are largely powered by the Remita payment network, supported by the federal government's Treasury Single Account (TSA) policy. The TSA was created in April 2012 and became effective after President Muhammadu Buhari directed all ministries, departments, and agencies (MDAs) to terminate commercial bank accounts and transfer to the government account by September 15, 2015. The TSA project developed an independent revenue e-collection method, requiring the government to collect income in a single account for proper cash management (Taiwo, 2015).

2.1.7 Online Admission Processing

Online admission processing is a method where candidates apply for admission through an institution's website, eliminating the need for physical visits to pick up hard copies of forms. This reduces the stress and hassles associated with visiting institutions for admissions. Candidates can fill out the form from anywhere, thereby eliminating the need to queue and wait for answers at tertiary institutions' offices (Bakar, 2009). Data is easily filtered through automated verification processes, ensuring only eligible candidates apply. This system also eliminates the need for deputing personnel to address candidate or guardian queries and distribute admission forms, allowing institutes to focus on other activities. The process is accurate, reliable, simple, user-friendly, and dynamic, facilitating the selection of successful candidates (Paras, 2017).

2.1.8 Relationship between E-administration and Service Delivery

The National Policy on Education in Nigeria mandates tertiary institutions to provide high-level manpower for national development through teaching, learning, and research. In the 21st century, educational institutions worldwide are benefiting from the shift from manual to ICT-based service delivery. According to Chukwuemeka, Ubochi, and Okechukwu (2017), this shift is essential as it reduces waste, delays, and mistakes in workers' duties. E-administration enables tertiary institutions to improve efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance service delivery systems. It also reduces storage requirements, allows data access by multiple individuals, and provides better security systems (Danda, 2004).

Also, data can be coded, which requires fewer staff to enforce the system. Databases can be used to manage personnel electronically, allowing for easier and more efficient decision-making. A more informed administration can better understand and exercise its rights, leading to a reduction in knowledge gaps on administration and quality assurance issues. Digital administration ensures that staff are no longer passive in their duties but actively choose the services they want and the best structure to provide (Sharma, 2010).

Tertiary institutions in Nigeria are increasingly utilising electronic mediums for administration and information dissemination. Information and communication technology (ICT) has become a global phenomenon, and its application, according to Jude and Dankoro (2012), is pivotal to the technological advancement of any nation, especially in the 21st century. As rightly captured by Edidiong, Nse, Iniobong, and Eno (2015), the verdict is that the ICT revolution has brought in its wake an education revolution that has changed the way services are rendered. In this direction, software programmes and specifically equipped computers are already providing learning

opportunities that emphasise exploration, problem-solving creativity, and innovation techniques in libraries.

Online applications enable users to access a wide variety of information resources and use advanced materials from digital libraries. Power networks enable interconnecting videos, podcasts, and web conferencing. The convergence of e-administration and service delivery in Nigeria is focused on how higher institutions use information and communication technology for effective service delivery. The need for educational administrators in Nigerian tertiary institutions to acquire electronic literacy skills cannot be ignored; every modern administrator ought to acquire knowledge and skill in information technology and to use the internet to browse to obtain or circulate information that will enhance organisational productivity and efficiency in their jurisdictions (Osakede, Ijimakinwa, Arijeniwa, Adesanya, & Ojo, 2017).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Davis (1989)

The theory adopted for this study is the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) proposed by Davis (1989). TAM is an information systems theory that models how users come to accept and use a technology. Davis (1989) presented a theoretical model aiming to predict and explain information and communication technology usage behaviour, that is, what causes potential adopters to accept or reject the use of information technology. This model, however, implies that emerging information technology cannot deliver improved organisational effectiveness if it is not accepted and used by potential users. The technology acceptance model is one of the most successful measurements for computer usage effectiveness among practitioners and academics (Kamel, 2004). According to the model, technology adoption is a function of a variety of factors, including relative advantage and ease of use. The two particular beliefs addressed by the Technology Acceptance Model are:

Perceived Usefulness (PU): This refers to the prospective user's subjective probability that using a specific application system will increase his or her job performance within an organisational context.

Perceived ease of use (PEOU): This refers to the degree to which the prospective user expects the target system to be free of effort.

Perceived usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) scales are as follows:

a. Perceived Usefulness

- i. Work more quickly

- ii. Job performance
 - iii. Increased productivity
 - iv. Effectiveness
 - v. Makes job easier
 - vi. Useful
- b. Perceived Ease of Use**
- i. Easy to learn
 - ii. Clear and understandable
 - iii. Easy to become skilful
 - iv. Easy to use
 - v. Controllable
 - vi. Easy to remember

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) aims at studying how individual perceptions affect intentions to use information technology as well as actual usage. TAM suggests that when users are presented with a new technology, a number of factors determine their decision about how and when they will use it. The attitude towards adoption will determine the adopter's positive or negative behaviour in the future concerning new technology. Perceived usefulness is “the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance,” and perceived ease of use, on the other hand, refers to “the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort” (Davis, 1989).

2.2.2 Application of Technology Acceptance Model to the Study

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a crucial theoretical framework for e-administration, as it focuses on the adoption of information and communication technology (ICT) tools. The success of ICT implementation depends on the adopter's positive or negative behaviour towards new technology. TAM explains two constructs: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, which are fundamental determinants of a technology system's use and predict attitudes towards its use.

The factors affecting the successful implementation of ICT in service delivery at Akwa Ibom State University depend on the user's willingness and attitudes towards using the new technology. The application of ICT in administration and service delivery at the target school was based on the perception that ICT would increase productivity, job performance, effectiveness, and make work easier and quicker.

Students' acceptance and utilisation of ICT are largely influenced by their attitudes and perceptions of the ease of use of the system. Students are more likely to effectively utilise the service delivery process using ICT if they perceive the system as being easy to use, easy to learn, easy to remember, clear and understandable, easy to become skilled at, and controllable. Thus, the adoption of this model is very relevant in conducting a study on the subject matter.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ali & Saeed's (2016) study assessed the impact of the moderating role of e-administration on training, performance appraisal, and organisational performance. The study population was comprised of employees working in twenty-five (25) companies where e-administration was in place. Based on a probability/simple random design, 245 employees were sampled, and 220 employees responded to a structured questionnaire, giving a response rate of 81%. The study revealed the significance of e-administration as a strategic element in improving organisational performance. E-administration moderates the relationship between performance appraisal and organisational performance as it plays a vital role in appraising the job performance of employees in a transparent manner. It reduces the chances of bias and other errors like leniency or strictness.

Allen *et al.* (2011) examined the shift towards electronic administration in government institutions in Libya to meet the challenges of the digital age. The study used a descriptive analytical approach and the field study method. To achieve the study objectives, a research methodology allowing for the collection of secondary data via literature review was used, and for primary data, questionnaires were used during a fieldwork exercise. Olufemi (2018) researched 'Information and Communication Technology (ICTs) in Nigeria, which changed the process of governance in the world. To manage government affairs for the benefit of citizens, governments have adopted e-governance technologies for service delivery. The objectives of this study were to provide a comprehensive review of e-governance in order to give it a sound framework, assess the levels of e-governance implementation, and evaluate critical success factors of e-governance implementation. An analysis of the impact of e-governance on service provision in Nigeria is also provided. It notes that Nigeria is facing a number of challenges with the introduction of e-government. Given the importance of the successful implementation of electronic governance services and from a practical perspective, the paper suggests that the government should take a positive position towards the factors that will bring about effective and efficient e-governance in Nigeria. The government should declare access to ICT services a fundamental human right for

every Nigerian, establish a timetable, and guarantee an enabling environment for attracting the right level of investment. The paper concludes that there is a lot of hope in the potential of e-governance to transform the internal efficiency of government and the relationship of government with citizens.

A study by Onyije and Opara (2018) on Information and Communication Technologies (ICT): A panacea to Achieving Effective Goals in Institutional Administration, the study examined the use of information and communication technology (ICT) by institutional administrators for effective administration. The study stated the need for effective use of ICT by institutional administrators in maintaining and controlling, according to policies laid down by the governing bodies of the institution. The findings of the research revealed various ICT resources used for effective institutional administration. It also revealed the extent of the utility of ICT to a tax administration's core operations but ignored key variables such as ICT capacity in terms of ICT skills, values, relationships, knowledge, and attitudes.

A study conducted by Maranga (2017) on the "Effect of e-government on Public Service Delivery in Kenya: A Study of Social Welfare Services The study adopts the survey research design and chi-square as tools of analysis. The study found that the implementation of e-governance in the social welfare service has metamorphosed into better service delivery. Another study conducted by Ojochogwu and Akpa (2017) on the effect of e-government on employees work and personal lives in Obajana cement factory used a qualitative research design with a sample of 115 employees. The empirical results showed valuable insights into the effects of e-governance on employees work and family domains. It was evident from the data that the effect of e-governance was predominantly perceived as positive, although some negative influence was also experienced.

Dada (2016) provided a review of academic literature on the failure of e-governance in developing countries. There exist wide gaps between the current reality in developing countries and the future of e-governance systems. The literature adopts content analysis as a research methodology, while the study finds out that the gaps are classified into three types: a hard-soft gap, implying a gap between the technology and the social context in which it is supplied; a private-public gap, suggesting that what works in the private sector may not work in the public sector; and a country context gap, which arises from the application of the same e-governance systems for both developing and developed countries. The paper recommends that administrators in developing countries must assess the situation at hand before implementing e-governance, which necessitates keeping an eye on challenges and propositions.

Peter, Gabriel Simon; Dr Sunday Ibanga & Prof. Nkanikpo Ibok

In a study by Sharma *et al.* (2012), they brought an example of the application of e-administration in Chile to notice, where they pointed out that the new administration is delivering online assessments within twelve hours as opposed to the 25 working days used hitherto. Also, in Costa Rica, as presented by Sharma *et al.* (2012), the utilisation of e-administration enabled citizens to get information about government organisations and interact with them through the internet. The researchers went further to show that in the Dominican Republic, the application of e-administration has been used to fight corruption in the bureaucracy, as the government website publishes the entry and exit assets of public administrators, their bank account details, and home addresses to help citizens detect possible fraudulent acts committed by public servants while in office. According to Sharma *et al.* (2012), in the Philippines, customs reform was pointed out as a prominent example of the use of e-administration in government and public administration. Sharma *et al.* (2012) pointed out in their study that the Philippines Custom Bureau has developed an online system to process clearance of imports, payment of duty, and delivery of release orders for shipments to leave the docks. This online system has lessened the cost of trade for businesses, reduced opportunities for fraud, and helped the bureau to maximize revenue collection.

Sunil *et al.* (2004), in their study of the effect of information technology investment on customers' satisfaction, hypothesised that IT investment is positively related to perceived quality and perceived value. Findings from the study revealed that IT investment has a greater positive effect on perceived quality and perceived value for firms in the service sector than firms in the manufacturing sector. The study revealed that IT investment is positively related to customer and market focus, process management, and the firm's performance.

Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study used descriptive and survey designs to analyse the major variables of e-administration at Akwa Ibom State University. A questionnaire (face-validated by two experts, one from the Department of Public Administration and one from the Department of Marketing, all from the Faculty of Management Sciences), was used to collect demographic data, and questions related to objectives and variables were asked. Visual data was gathered from observing facilities and infrastructure. The primary sources of data include interviews, questionnaires, and personal experiences. Secondary sources included textbooks, journals, and internet articles related to the subject.

Peter, Gabriel Simon; Dr Sunday Ibanga & Prof. Nkanikpo Ibok

Akwa Ibom State University is a conventional, multi-campus institution. The main campus is located in Ikot Akpaden, Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. It adjoins the confluence of Ikot Akpaden - Eastern Obolo Road and Eket - Ikot Abasi Highway. The next campus is located at Obio Akpa, Oruk Anam Local Government Area, along Abak - Ikot Okoro Road. This campus of the University is located at latitude 4°58'13.48" North and longitude 7°45'24.76" East. It has a sub-urban setting, adjoining Abak town, and is within twenty minutes' drive from Uyo.

The estimated population for this study was one thousand five hundred and forty-eight (1548) students and four hundred and seventeen staff, from which a sample of 400 respondents was selected as determined by the Taro Yamane formula at 0.05% level of significance. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency tables, weighted mean, and simple percentages (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 19). Correlation analysis was used to measure the strength or degree of association between variables. In addition, regression analysis was used in order to estimate or predict the impact of electronic administration on service delivery.

1. Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Result

Data was collected through the administration of questionnaires to the selected respondents in Akwa Ibom State University. A total of four hundred (400) questionnaires were administered to the selected respondents. These questionnaires were retrieved immediately after completion. Out of the four hundred (400) questionnaires administered, three hundred and seventy-six (376) were correctly completed and returned to the researcher, while 24 were rejected as a result of missing questions by the respondents, and wrongly filled-out ones.

4.1 Online admission processing and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.

This analysis relates to the first research question, "What extent has online admission processing affected service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University?"

Peter, Gabriel Simon; Dr Sunday Ibanga & Prof. Nkanikpo Ibok

Table 4.2: Results of Analysis of online admission processing and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University

ITEM NO.	RESEARCH STATEMENTS/ITEMS	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A) (U)	Undecided (D)	Disagree (SD)	Strongly Disagree
1	I utilized the online admission processing in Akwa Ibom State University	94(25%)	132(35.1%) 99(26.3%)		24(6.4%)	27(7.2%)
2	Utilization of online admission processing saves time	104(27.7%)	146(38.8%) 65(17.3%)		46(12.2%)	15(4.0%)
3	Making use of online admission processing into Akwa Ibom State University is less expensive	122(32.4%)	58(14.6%) 93(23.5%)		66(16.7%)	37(9.3%)
4	Utilization of online admission processing has increased the number of applicants applying for admission into Akwa Ibom State University	66(17.6%)	109(29%) 88(23.4%)		76(20.2%)	37(9.8%)
5	The online admission processing made it easy to complete the process despite my distance from the Akwa Ibom State University Campus	49(13%)	130(34.6%) 95(25.3%)		68(18.1%)	34(9.0%)

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 4.2 shows that, on the research statement that people utilised the online admission processing in Akwa Ibom State University, 94 or 25% of the respondents strongly agreed, 132 or 35.1% agreed, 99 or 26.3% were undecided, 39 or 10.4% strongly disagreed, 24 or 6.4% disagreed, and 27 or 7.2% strongly disagreed. On the research statement that utilisation of online admission processing saves time, 104, or 27.7%, of the respondents strongly agreed, and 146 or 38.8% agreed. 65 or 17.3% were undecided, 46 or 12.2% disagreed, while 15 or 4.0% strongly disagreed. On the statement that the use of online admission processing into Akwa Ibom State University is less expensive, 122 or 32.4% strongly agreed, 58 or 14.6% agreed, 93 or 23.5% were undecided, 66 or 16.7% disagreed, while 37 or 9.3% strongly disagreed. On the research statement that the Utilization of online admission processing has increased the number of applicants applying for admission into Akwa Ibom State University, 66 or 17.6% of the respondents strongly agreed, 109 or 29% agreed. 88 or 23.4% were undecided, 76 or

Peter, Gabriel Simon; Dr Sunday Ibanga & Prof. Nkanikpo Ibok

20.2% disagreed, while 37 or 9.3% strongly disagreed. Finally, on the research statement that online admission processing made it easy to complete the process despite my distance from the Akwa Ibom State University Campus, 49 or 13% of the respondents strongly agreed, 130 or 34.6% agreed, 95 or 25.3% were undecided, 68 or 18.1% disagreed, while 34 or 9.0% strongly disagreed.

4.2 Online payment method and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.

This analysis relates to the second research question, “How has utilisation of online payment methods impacted service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University?” The analysis is presented in

Table 4.3: Results of Analysis of online payment method and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.

ITEM NO.	RESEARCH STATEMENTS/ITEMS	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A) (U)	Undecided	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)
6	I utilize online payment method for fees in AKwa Ibom State University	202 (53.7%)	47 (12.5%) (16.5%)	62	33(8.8%)	32(8.5%)
7	Utilizing online fees payment in Akwa Ibom State University is stress-free	103(27.4%)	141(37.5%) (95(25.3%))		11(2.9%)	26(6.9%)
8	Payment of fees online in Akwa Ibom State University makes it possible to register courses without much verifications at the ICT Unit	88(23.4%)	147 (39.1%) (106(28.2%))		23(6.1%)	12(3.2%)
9	Payment of fees via the online payment method can be done at any time of the day	67(17.3%)	118(31.4%) (73(19.4%))		83(22.1%)	35(9.3%)
10	Online payment of fees in Akwa Ibom State University allows for payment of fees without missing lectures	127(33.8%)	182(48.4%)	2(0.5%)	38(10.1%)	27(7.2%)

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 4.3 shows that, on the research statement that people utilise online payment methods for fees in Akwa Ibom State University, 202 or 53.7% of the respondents strongly agreed, 47 or 12.5% agreed, 62 or 16.5% were undecided, 33 or 8.8% disagreed, while 32 or 8.5% strongly disagreed. On the research statement that utilising online fee payment methods in Akwa Ibom State University is stress-free, 103

Peter, Gabriel Simon; Dr Sunday Ibanga & Prof. Nkanikpo Ibok

or 27.4% of the respondents strongly agreed, 141 or 37.5% agreed, 95 or 25.3% were undecided, 11 or 2.9% disagreed, while 26 or 7.9% strongly disagreed. On the research statement that payment of fees online in Akwa Ibom State University makes it possible to register for courses without much verification at the ICT Unit, 88 or 23.4% of the respondents strongly agreed, 147 or 39.1% agreed, 106 or 28.2% were undecided, 79 or 6.1% disagreed while 12 or 3.2% of the respondents strongly disagreed. On the research statement that payment of fees via the online payment method can be done at any time of the day, 67 or 17.3% of the respondents strongly agreed, 118 or 31.4% agreed, 73 or 19.4% were undecided, 83 or 22.1% disagreed, while 35 or 9.3 % strongly disagreed. On the research statement that Online payment of fees in Akwa Ibom State University allows for payment of fees without missing lectures, 127 or 33.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, 182 or 48.4% agreed, 2 or 0.5% were undecided, 38 or 10.1% disagreed while 27 or 7.2% strongly disagreed.

4.2 Computer-based testing and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.

This analysis relates to the third research question, “To what extent has the utilisation of computer-based testing (CBT) impacted service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University?”

Table 4.4: Results of Analysis of computer-based testing and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.

		Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A) Undecided (U)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)
11	I have used the computer -based testing (CBT)for Continuous Assessment in Akwa Ibom State University	55(14.6%)	136(36.2%) 112(29.8%)	48(12.8%)	25 (6.6%)
12	I have used the CBT for Semester Examination in Akwa Ibom State University	82 (21.8%)	113 (30.1%) 133(35.4%)	33 (8.8%)	15 (4.0%)
13	The use of CBT in tests and Exams has reduced examination malpractice)	229(60.9%)	51(13.6%) 69 (18.4%)	9(2.4%)	18(4.8%)
14	The utilization of CBT for examinations has reduced instances of missing scripts	52(13.8%)	163 (43.4%) 126 (33.5%)	27 (7.2%)	8(2.1%)
15	The use of CBT for examinations comes with challenges like power outage	179 (47.6%)	111(31.4%) 58 (15.4%)	10(2.7%)	11 (2.9%)

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Peter, Gabriel Simon; Dr Sunday Ibanga & Prof. Nkanikpo Ibok

Table 4.4 shows that, on the research statement that I have used computer-based testing (CBT) for continuous assessment in Akwa Ibom State University, 55 or 14.6% of the respondents strongly agreed, 136 or 36.2% agreed, 112 or 36.2% were undecided, 48 or 12.8% disagreed, while 25 or 6.6% strongly disagreed. On the research statement that I have used the CBT for semester examinations in Akwa Ibom State University, 82 or 21.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, 113 or 30.1% agreed, 133 or 35.4% were undecided, 33 or 8.8% disagreed, while 15 or 4.0% strongly disagreed. On the research statement that the use of CBT in tests and exams has reduced examination malpractice, 229 or 60.9% of the respondents strongly agreed, 51 or 13.6% agreed, 69 or 18.4% were undecided, 9 or 2.4% disagreed, while 18 or 4.8% strongly disagreed. On the research statement that the utilisation of CBT for examinations has reduced instances of missing scripts, 52 or 13.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, 163 or 43.4% agreed, 126 or 33.5% were undecided, 27 or 7.2% disagreed, while 8 or 2.1% of the respondents strongly disagreed. Finally, on the research statement that the use of CBT for examinations comes with challenges like power outages, 179 or 47.6% of the respondents strongly agreed, 118 or 31.4% agreed, 58 or 15.4% were undecided, 10 or 2.7% disagreed, while 11 or 2.9% strongly disagreed.

4.4 Correlation Analysis of the Variables

Correlation analysis using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation method was adopted to determine the degree of association between the variables in the study.

Table 4.5: Results of Correlation Analysis of Variable

Correlations				
	OAP	OPM	CBT	SD
Pearson Correlation	1	.304**	.218**	.319**
OAP Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
N	376	376	376	376
Pearson Correlation	.304**	1	.353**	.201**
OPM Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
N	376	376	376	376
Pearson Correlation	.218**	.353**	1	.111*
CBT Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.031
N	376	376	376	376
Pearson Correlation	.319**	.201**	.111*	1
SD Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.031	
N	376	376	376	376

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024)

Peter, Gabriel Simon; Dr Sunday Ibanga & Prof. Nkanikpo Ibok

There is a low to high level of association between the variables in the study, as shown in Table 4.5. The bivariate PPMC correlation coefficients for online admission processing (OAP), online payment method (OPM), computer-based testing (CBT), and service delivery (SD) show this. This is because the correlation coefficient obtained for the variables between the dependent variable, service delivery, and the independent variables ranged from 0.111 to 0.353. It is an indication of a low to high positive association between these variables. This implies the use of online admission processing (OAP), online payment methods (OPM), and computer-based testing (CBT) associated with service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.

Discussion of Findings

5.1 Online admission processing and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.

As shown in Table 4.2, there is a positive and significant relationship between online admission processing and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University. This is an indication that the increased level of online admission processing led to efficient service delivery in the institution. Implying that with the utilisation of online admission processing, data are easily filtered through automated verification processes so that only eligible candidates can apply. Institutes no longer require deputing personnel to address a candidate's or guardian's query to distribute and collect admission forms. As a result of this, the institute can utilise manpower resources for other activities. With this, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between online admission processing and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University was therefore rejected, while the alternative was accepted. This result is in line with Paras (2015), who says that the process is very accurate and reliable due to limited human involvement and that it is simple, user-friendly, and very dynamic.

5.2 Online payment method and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.

The test of the relationship between online payment methods and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University was analysed using Table 4.3. It revealed that increased use of the online payment method has helped in the reduction of stress and time wastage by students. This is an indication of advancement in the use of ICT in the institution. This analysis invalidates the hypothesis that states there is no significant relationship between online payment methods and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University, as the result of this research supports the assertion that online payment methods improve prompt payment and safe delivery and prevent management and students from

becoming financially frustrated (Jelilove & Musa, 2016; Mustapha, 2018; Omotubora & Basu, 2018).

5.2 Computer-based testing and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.

Our finding on Table 4.4 shows there is a significant relationship between computer-based testing and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University, as opposed to hypothesis three (3), which states that there is no significant relationship between the utilisation of computer-based testing (CBT) and service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University. This is the result of the increased use of ICT in the institution and its attendant advantages. Akwa Ibom State University, as an educational institution, is benefiting from the shift from manual to ICT-based service delivery. According to Chukwuemeka, Ubochi, and Okechukwu (2017), this shift is essential because the use of ICT in work-related activities reduces waste of time, delays, and mistakes on the part of workers in the discharge of their duties. There is no limit to the use of computers for educational administration.

6 Summary of Findings

This research study was carried out to examine the effect of e-administration on service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University. In order to validate the work theoretically and empirically, literature relevant to the subject matter were reviewed. The study adopted simple percentage analysis, correlation, and simple regression analysis in analysing the data generated. The data analysed show that:

1. Online admission processing had a positive and significant effect on service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.
2. Online payment methods also had a positive and significant effect on service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.
3. Computer-based test (CBT) had a positive and significant effect on service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University.

6.1 Conclusion

This study is based on the effect of e-administration in Nigerian tertiary institutions with reference to Akwa Ibom State (AKSU). It provides information on the current level of university attainment in the use of e-administration (application of ICT) towards enhancing efficient service delivery. Based on the findings, the study revealed that online admission processing, online payment methods, and computer-based test all significantly impacted service delivery in Akwa Ibom State University within the period

Peter, Gabriel Simon; Dr Sunday Ibanga & Prof. Nkanikpo Ibok

under review. The study concluded that most tertiary institutions, especially Akwa Ibom State University, have keyed into the e-administrative system of management for the core areas of their activities. Some of the areas where ICT has been used include selection and admission of new entrants, post-UTME and in-course examinations, use of email services for general administration, fee payment, and electronic library. Automation of admissions processes has enhanced registration exercise in Nigerian universities. These institutions have, to a reasonable extent, adopted automated admission processes for prospective students. In this regard, entrance forms are purchased online, as are acceptance of admission, payment of fees, and course registration. The e-process has made the enrollment exercise less cumbersome.

6.2 Recommendations

Based on the result of the study, it is therefore recommended that:

1. E-administration should be seen and adopted as an important step towards enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of service delivery in Nigerian universities. The institution, through their management, should therefore ensure that e-administration is adopted through the embrace of different aspects such as online admission processing, online selection, and screening of prospective students.
2. There should be a purposeful attempt to revitalise the ICT units of universities by way of beefing up ICT gadgets with upgraded versions to assuage the needs and aspirations of users, especially with regards to modern and advanced user-friendly online payment methods via websites.
3. There should be frequent training and retraining of staff in the ICT unit to keep them abreast of the recent trends in technology. This will not only enhance the implementation of e-administration but will generally improve service delivery.

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